
CONCEPTUAL PHYSICAL EDUCATION: A COURSE FOR FUTURE

Loksha K R

College Director

Dept. of Physical Education, Government College, for Women (Autonomous),
Mandya, Karnataka State

ABSTRACT

Most people still believe that Physical Education or Movement Education is merely an activity programme which involves some play, skill learning and practice. Those who really understand today's physical education and sports as a Scientific, Social phenomenon numerically are very few. As a field of activity, physical education marked by variety. Games, Recreation, Fitness programmes, Yoga, Adventure Sports etc, all comprise physical education. Irrespective of age, Sex, Geographical and cultural boundaries, one can choose any activity one likes to participate in. In the present study an effort is made to put forward an objective point of view on matters of vital most concern to physical education in modern life.

Key-Words: Physical Education, Physical Fitness, Modern life, Need, Importance,

INTRODUCTION:

The human body is a sacred gift of Nature. Its Growth, Development and efficiency largely depends upon the quality and quantity of motor activities it performs. Strength and Fitness were crucial factors for protection against wild animals and search of food. With the onset of Cultural Revolution, man began to break away his natural habitat and rendered himself comparatively physically weaker to animals. In ancient times, man engaged in strenuous activities like hunting for livelihood, seeking protection from wild animals, gathering food, fighting for protection. In the modern era, man is dependent on machines for his livelihood, suffers from physical and mental stress and discomfort due to severe lack of physical activity, and is deprived of the principle of education, a blissful life. Also, it can be said that it is a tragedy today that children are not involved in games due to over population in cities and lack of space. Nervous system is adversely affected due to physical disability and death of disuse organs. It is a fact seen in all countries that anti-social behavior like crime and juvenile delinquency is increasing in the society due to lack of activities that manifest itself fully.

Millions of years ago man was engaged in physical labor for livelihood by walking with the help of legs as well as hands; blood circulation in the body was easy. But a drastic change in his posture (evolutionary) from moving perpendicular to the ground on the basis of the legs makes the flow of blood to the brain extremely difficult due to gravity, making it necessary to perform consistent exercises due to fluctuations in brain function. Changes in the human body since evolution and the hectic lifestyle of today's mechanized life emphasize the need for physical activities.

PHYSICAL EDUCATION:

The word **Physical** refers to body, and indicates bodily characteristics such as strength, speed, endurance, flexibility, coordination and performance. The word **Education** when used in conjunction with physical, refers to a process of education that develops the human body especially fitness and movement skills. ⁽¹⁾

The general Aim of Physical education as given by Herbert Spencer is “preparation of individuals for complete living” (complete living in respect of Growth, Development, Adjustment, Personality, etc.)

The aim of physical education is the wholesome development of the personality of an individual physically fit, mentally alerts, emotionally balanced, socially well adjusted, morally true and spiritually uplifted.⁽²⁾

From an overview of various definitions of various Physical Educationalists the following salient features of physical education emerges;

Physical Education is the only unique discipline which uses “Physical Activity” as the medium for human development. Its approach to its objectives is natural and unambiguous.⁽³⁾

Physical education not simply a biological necessity, it is part and parcel of man’s social inheritance and social interaction.

Importance / Benefits of Physical Education Activities:

Today's education gives special importance to the materialistic collection and is not perfect in shaping physical fitness and personality. Failure to provide experiences and guidance to the present youth generation to face life's problems with courage, boldness and accept life's victories and defeats equally. Many images and circumstances that shake the balance of the mind at the stage of adolescence are seen daily in front of children in different styles. Many social ills and deadly diseases are the brainchild of children growing up in such an environment, from which the society is reeling. We have forgotten that only intellect can be trained through study and youth is the passion, strength and hope of the nation. All is wasted if the energy and enthusiasm of the youth should be properly harnessed and channeled into worthy and benevolent channels.

In addition to the physical development of an individual, nothing can be said to be as influential as physical education in the harmonious development of mental well-being, social competence, emotional balance and health. Considering all these things, it is welcome that physical education has been given importance in today's educational program. Engaging in consistent and systematic physical education can provide the following benefits to students physically, mentally and emotionally.

1) Increase physical fitness and promote long-term health benefits:

Participating in healthy recreational activities and sports can develop a person's physical fitness components such as muscular strength, muscular endurance, stamina, and endurance. Maintaining a balanced body fat helps prevent obesity, control blood pressure; prevent high cholesterol, diabetes and heart disease. As lung capacity and body efficiency increase, the chances of lung related diseases are less. Several scientific research reports have shown that physical activities improve the quality of bones and make a person have strong bones even in old age and partially prevent many diseases. Physical Education stimulates vital organs of the body for a “supreme effort”. Used as therapeutic measure, Physical activity must help individual to improve body Posture and eliminates physical deformities.

2) Benefits of physical education beyond physical health:

Beyond physical health, how sports affect our mental health can be understood from neurological, psychological and social sources.

(i) Neurological Benefits:

In relation to physical development in the brain, sports release dopamine and Serotonin. As a result, our risk of depression is reduced by up to 30%. These happy chemicals are essential for a stable and positive mood. Any form of exercise stimulates the production of these, but sports seem to do so most effectively. For example, when we score a goal or win a game.

(ii) Psychological Benefits:

Sport is a form of competition that has amazing psychological benefits for our well-being. Sports reduce our anxiety levels by releasing tension and increasing mental strength. In sports the purpose and goal is clear and when one wins by scoring more points than other teams, this sense of achievement also boosts self-confidence. It is when we lose that we learn about our resilience.

Helping to deal with mental problems like anxiety, depression and losing and winning in sports and maintaining mental balance. Those who can face victory and defeat in sports with equanimity face happiness and sorrow equally in life. Experiences in sports allow students to inculcate leadership qualities. Reduce the risk of stress, anxiety and depression and provide an outlet (release) for stress.

In many cases, it hurts to lose. But youngsters must learn to pick themselves up and keep moving towards to the next game or the next season. Physical education and sports enable the individuals to learn how to handling or balance emotions throughout their life time.

It enhance an individual's ability to concentrate and maintain focus and help the individual to relive their academic stress and anxiety by developing sufficient knowledge and insight to make suitable decisions and arrive at feasible solutions. It helps to prepare an individual for making worthy use of leisure

(iii) Improved Social Skills:

Traits of Personality are inherited but Quality of characters is acquired. Physical Education offer unlimited opportunities to the individual to develop the Strong social characters. Many people in the modern world lack social interaction. There is no mistaking that sport is a way of making friends and reaping all the benefits of living with them. Promote a healthy lifestyle, enable the individual to interact healthily and successfully with others and strengthen good relationships among others.

Team sports are especially good for developing social virtues. Team sports are one of the best tools for achieving cooperative spirit, friendliness, cooperation, honesty, sportsmanship, respect for the rights of others as well as promoting self-discipline, selflessness, belongingness, giving importance to others, non-discrimination etc. Sense of Fair play, Honesty, Co-operation, Friendliness, justice etc. are practiced and learned during play as a concomitant process and transferred to life situations. Playfields, therefore, a Breeding Ground for strong social character development. Playfields are the levelers of inequalities, through sports program, it breaks down groups and racial prejudices, broadens outlook and avoids narrow feelings among competitors. Participating in recreational and physical activities helps to cultivate social virtues such as respect for others, responsibility, harmony with others, cooperative spirit, non-competition, the mindset that everyone is the same, and being aware of our work responsibilities.

CONCLUSION

Toning the body helps to delay aging and helps to enjoy life more happily, removes unwanted body fat and improves beauty and reduces cholesterol levels. Evidence for the benefits of physical education is that it contributes to a longer and healthier life by reducing the risk of major diseases such as diabetes, high blood pressure and heart disease. In order to enjoy free time, a person should participate in activities that are refreshing to the mind and socially acceptable. Participating in activities brings joy to the soul, rejuvenating the body as well as all-round development of the individual and suggests avenues for utilization of free time.

Allow for the display of latent talent, promote friendliness, cooperation, honesty, sportsmanship, respect for the rights of others and self-discipline. Physical activities help us boost self-esteem and confidence. It helps us to increase the quality of life by building a positive self-image. Therefore, it is better to participate in sports and other physical activities for good health. Physical education as an integral part of total education is limited to discussion. It is a tragedy that till today this basic subject has not been taken as a part of education and has been neglected. "Health is fortune" is a saying that is accepted by all of us from intellectuals to common citizens. But the priority given to physical education, which is the main means of attaining such health, is lacking. Even now, the effort to strengthen physical education in the educational base needs to be started.

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